

Day 2 of TOPS October 2022 Community Panel
October 6, 2022
[Video Recording](#)

Key:

Time markers

Important points/questions

BEGINNING OF TRANSCRIPT - Note this transcript may contain errors, please view the recording to confirm speakers and text.

Yvonne Ivey

Alright. Today, we're just going to kick things off. If you get to the next slide...you have AGU providing an update on OpenCore. Housekeeping: everyone should have access to the WiFi. If you don't, please let us know. And bathrooms are across the hall. But if you're at home, I'll let you navigate WiFi and bathrooms yourself.

We strongly encourage folks to engage with us on social media via these two hashtags: #ToOPenSci and #IHeartOpenScience

Alright, we're going to jump into the code of conduct right now. And we've been following this code of conduct over the past year. We'd like everyone to create a safe space, whether in the virtual sense or here in the room. I also ask everyone to treat all participants with respect and consideration as our core values around diversity, equity and inclusion. And we expect folks to be considerate, respectful and collaborative in this. Please avoid any personal attacks. And if there are any situations where you feel like there's been unacceptable behavior, whether that's harassment, intimidation or discrimination in any form, please contact the meeting host directly. And you can see the meeting host's email address is on the screen, but also, we can drop it in the chat. Chelle Gentleman is the host for today's meeting. And as usual, our goal is to be as inclusive and collaborative as possible. And to do that, we need your feedback and suggestions. So please engage with us. We have a QR code on the screen right now, but we also ask folks to log into the feedback tool and chat with us.

Alright, this is the snapshot of today's agenda. As I shared, the focus will really be on our TOPS Open Science Curriculum update by AGU. And so, with that, trying to keep us on track for timing, I will hand it off to Brooks Hanson, who will be presenting for AGU.

Brooks Hanson

So, thank you all. Let me start. One thing... a great set of conversations yesterday and I was really reflecting on that and I've revised this slide deck three or four times trying to think about how to build off of both – reflect the schedule and an update on and other related things like Fall meeting this year and aspects like that, but also which were partly in the slide deck but in organized differently, thinking about some other aspects of larger culture change that we talked about... that was part of yesterday's conversation and things that emerging partnerships among societies with funders – obviously NASA, but worldwide – it could be leveraged, it could

include TOPS, going forward. So, I wanted to add a little bit of, I hope, richness to that conversation too in thinking about how TOPS just isn't for us (a completion project), it fits into a larger strategy and goal set that I think aligns with several other key societies, obviously federal governments, worldwide governments and so forth. And how do we get working together?

Also, I want to raise a couple of risks that we see if TOPS succeeds widely and how do we might prepare and think about that as well? Those are good risks because that means TOPS is really successful, but it's going to really push parts of the other infrastructure and systems in ways that we need to think about. And that was one of the things I thought was missing from the conversation yesterday. So, this is the TOPS team. Laura and Kristina are here. A couple of educational experts and Chris Herman just left to go to the Michael J. Fox Foundation. And so, we also have an open position for him. And then another open kind of contractor open science expert position that we will be moving very quickly on.

Next slide. And so, I just want very quickly... open science is a key part of AGU's strategic plan. The blue surf on the left was adopted in 2017. The five objectives that we are focusing on (this was just presented to our board last week) that we're really focusing on over the next several years are these... and so you can see open science as part of that. So, we just emphasized that. And obviously TOPS is one part of that in a larger framework.

And very quickly, next slide. I put this slide in almost all my presentations because this is driving those objectives on the previous slide. And I think this follows up heavily with our conversations yesterday. **This is what we view is the imperative for open science and culture change in science.** It's that... and in many ways the culture can change...the conversation we were having yesterday is actually bigger. Most of our science infrastructure is not well aligned for these problems. They're not in... convergence science is happening, but it's happening in spite of or on top of the structure that we have. Our funding structure is very disciplinary based. Our society structure is very disciplinary based, and our institutional structure is very disciplinary based, and that's not going to break anytime soon. So, we're working on top of that to really think about how to do this. **And I think that also is why open science is very important. It's obviously a key communication with the public, but it's working across disciplines in ways that have not happened in the past.** So obviously there is cross-disciplinary work. Some of that is happening, but it's happening on top of a science infrastructure, our core science infrastructure with funding societies, institutions that are not really fully aligned to support that. So obviously things like pay or promotion, I think things to get tenure and promotion who are doing interdisciplinary research, pick a publisher who are doing interdisciplinary research, all of those things are part of that.

So next slide. So, these next two slides are topics that I'm happy to go into. I want, obviously I want to hit some of these today. So, in some ways this is not going to be a very linear presentation and Yvonne... so, there's actually section breaks for all of these. If we decide to move around...I just want to give you an overall outline of...just reflecting yesterday and we were talking about a whole bunch of things and an overall outline. And so it may be that our conversation goes down one place and you say, 'oh, we've gotten this...' we want to learn more about badges and how the assessment of the OpenCore is going to work. Let's jump over to there. So, I just wanted to give you kind of an outline of where I was thinking of presenting.

I can go through this linearly, but if we decide to be non-linear, go to another topic...very, very happy to do that depending on how the conversation goes... and if there is something towards the end that we really want to hit... happy to do that. So, the first couple points are kind of the culture primarily in the Earth and Space sciences, but also about other society partners that are working on that **convergence science and open science work** that I think TOPS can and I would use this word intentionally... partner with. And I think that was something Jim said yesterday too about for example, one of the societies that we're partnered with and need to... is AMA (American Mathematical). About 8 or 9% of our abstracts at our meeting are involved directly AI and machine learning. And that was up from like half a percent four years ago, five years ago. **So, we need to partner with AMA and computer scientists and others to really develop that science robustly.** That's just one example of convergence science that's going forward and really exploding. So, how we think about that.

And there are some of those society partnerships are really already forming and out there on open science, completely independent of TOPS and actually, in some cases, unaware of what TOPS is doing... though some of that society meeting engagement will help that next year. But there's a larger, many larger connections that are possible. And there's a lot we could talk about OpenCore, the progress we've made so far, some of the lessons and challenges and adjustments we've had to make, what the outreach engagement plan is. That's why I think we hit... we talked about 20,000 yesterday. I think we're very optimistic that we can have or exceed that fairly quickly. I think that was 20,000 over five years. I think we will be.... I'm hoping will be there very quickly. And I'm happy to go into some of what we're thinking about and the priorities for who we want to move through first and get your feedback on that.

This Fall meeting, we have a large open science focus including TOPS and more at this Fall meeting. And I was talking to Jim about how this feeds into next Fall meeting, where the theme will be open science... I can't tell you exactly what the theme is. I [will] lose my job and they'd have to shoot me and hang me. That theme will be unveiled at the Fall meeting this year, but it will be about open science. And that will be our theme for Fall meeting 2023. And then part of the TOPS is also an Open Science Award and how that fits into other society award structures.

Next slide. And then I couldn't all fit it on this one slide...next steps beyond the Open Core minimum viable product (MVP) or beta that we're working on. And some of that came up yesterday in adding disciplinary richness, keeping improving at how...and then how we're going to assess some of this came up yesterday... how are we going to assess is this working? We actually... I think we have some very good metrics. We're seeing what that uptake is and happy to go through those with you. And then we can go beyond what else are we missing in that assessment? How do we assess how quickly this is working over the course is valuable. Are people doing some of the things? Are people engaging in open science? I think there is a couple of things that... this challenge of culture change. I think I've heard – Brian's on – and I think I got this from him, but I think, Brian, you got it from somewhere else. And it's a pretty common quote about 'culture eats strategy'.

But there's also TOPS and we're finding this already in some of the work that we're doing. It is challenging the **open science infrastructure**: repository, the data repositories infrastructure and

the other services. I was talking to Jim about Jupyter Hub, but it's also the **people resources** that are in open science. So, a key part of the OpenCore and some of the conversations we have is engaged with open science communities. Are those communities ready for 20,000 people knocking on their door? And from what we've seen in some cases, yes. And in some cases: Oh my God. So, I'm happy to go through this linearly. Like I said, I'm going to take a little pause here. And Chelle, also, if there's something that's not on here that you all would like me to think about and put in and get to, but then happy to move forward, starting in a linear process or jump to anything else. And so those are what we were thinking of in the next two hours or so, two and a half hours of covering, but just wanted to make sure that that we have the right level set.

[12:13 minutes]

Yvonne Ivey

Let's put it to the panelists.

Malvika

So, Brooks, it's Malvika... I have a question around what do you mean by 'infrastructure and support will break'?

Referencing text on the slide under 'Key Risks'

Brooks Hanson

So, we are already finding from work that we are doing... that some, for example, and I can show data on this if we jump down to that — that domain repositories are not ready for — **some of the domain repositories – are not ready in terms of their capacity, in terms of how efficiently they can process data and in terms of the amount of data [they can] process.**

And I'm happy that we actually have data on that from work that we've already done. But TOPS is going to scale that by an order of magnitude. That's just and then it's...

Question/Speaker ??

Can you explain what domain repositories means? I'm not understanding.

Brooks Hanson

GenBank is an example of a data repository, PDB is an example of a data repository. So, in the Earth and space sciences, we have about 300 different domain repositories. The NASA DAACs (Distributed Active Archive Centers) are examples of that. Science Base at USGS, other things like that. So, versus the general repository would be... Zenodo, Dryad, Big Share – Harvard.

Chelle Gentemann

I would say that the infrastructure – like that conversation – so that actually fits within the Open-Source Science Initiative (OSSI) strategy – that [is] Steve Crawford's area. What TOPS focuses on is not the infrastructure but the community.

Brooks Hanson

Yep.

Chelle Gentemann

So, it's sort of a separate conversation.

Brooks Hanson

Yeah. So, my point is absolutely, Chelle. My point is this is going to really push that.

Chelle Gentemann

Yeah. Totally taken. And I think that that's a conversation for OSSI and Steve maybe...but it's something that they're actively working on and I think they would welcome a conversation about.

Jim:

So, the ways that technology is used to facilitate community... it seems like the in between zone of a Venn diagram... how does that fit in? **Who's responsible for ensuring that we set up the right digital platforms to facilitate the community work of the TOPS folks?**

Chelle Gentemann

Yeah, so that is – so within OSSI, there's sort of policy, core services, ROSES elements and TOPS. I got the slide in the right order even I think. They're all within the same office – so we all inform each other's activities. And so, the infrastructure part... is that core services that Steve Crawford and Elena are working on...

Yvonne Ivey

So, Steve is handling policies. So, how do we actually push down this change in a way that's regulated... and then we can see across all the federal agencies – that shift. Elena Steponaitis is focused on the core services piece, so we're shifting everything. Are we actually building an infrastructure that will not break and are we continuing to support our users? So, Brooks referenced the DAACs, which are the data archives across Earth Science, but we have all of the other archives across NASA Science: Heliophysics Archives, Planetary Archives, Biological & Physical Sciences...Astro. And so, we have the other data archives who are also going to have to reshift the way that they not only work with their users, but push out data. And so, the concept is being framed as **core services**. So how do we truly build this structure – this core – that when we're asking folks to shift the way that they work and lean into open science practices, what's that infrastructure look like?

Chelle Gentemann

And so that is like...there are a *huge* number of conversations and workshops going on and that's why I'm just saying – this is covered over there and TOPS is informing – keeping an eye on it all. But that conversation sort of belongs over there. There are whole workshops on it.

Kevin Murphy

I was just going to basically say the same thing. We have a pretty large effort going on right now. **We're actually starting up a program office for core services. And core services are specifically the digital infrastructure needed to support open science within NASA.** We're not doing that in isolation. We're working together on it...with other agencies by discussing and learning from them and those types of things. I'm unclear what the risk is to the infrastructure.

Brooks Hanson

So, Kevin, I would say it's not...it's maybe not NASA's infrastructure. A lot of those repositories are... short term NSF funding. They're other...they move from NSF funding to other funding. Those are used...for example, already... we have in a whole bunch of publisher policies moving from supplements to encouraging authors to put data in repositories, ideally domain repositories.

Some of those are NASA, actually a small part of AGU journals go to NASA. We've quadrupled their volume going to that and that's really pushing their finances So, the leading practice that comes out of the OpenCore others is FAIR data. FAIR data involves data citations, depositing data in a repository. And I suspect some work that NASA's scientists are involved in either as fundees or direct NASA employees collaborating with others. **The best homes for the data might be multiple repositories.** Some cases of NASA repositories and the... So, I'm glad NASA has it, but I think... this was just a larger risk that... and I don't have any solutions and I appreciate Chelle... that there's a separate conversation on solutions.

Kevin Murphy

So, what your risk is...is that if you train people to use repositories to store their data or their software, that those repositories may not work.

Brooks Hanson

Correct. Or aren't ready for the volume they're going to have to deliver rapidly.

Kevin Murphy

Okay. So that's not a bad point. I think in terms of what NASA's doing... we're still trying to figure out some of those implementation activities related to our policy on open science. And we're kind of struggling through some of that now. But, yeah, I get what you're saying. The whole community at large may not be prepared... if all of the PIs (Principal Investigators) that get trained want to go put their data somewhere. Got it.

Yvonne Ivey

Alright. Let's just hop through the slides.

Fernando?

I am curious actually on this one, before we switch slides...could you expand a little bit on the second bullet on risks... (*Referencing text on slide that reads 'culture eats strategy for breakfast'*) ...I'm wondering, how are you thinking of that interplay between community and strategy? If I understand, I think of culture as like the emerging part, kind of the bottom-up emerging part of the community. And I think of strategy as kind of the top-down vision of where things should be headed and it seems like you're trying to capture something between those.

Brooks Hanson

So, Fernando, for now, what I'm going to say is... I think let's come back to that, because I think the conversation going through this where we identify some of the resistance, some of the cultural resistance, and some of that I already mentioned is kind of a misalignment of the science structure of funding... too. And so how do we work despite that and so forth. So, I think some of that will come through on where we're seeing resistance. And then how we address that

resistance. And the only thing I'll add, I'll mention this again, I was on a call this morning as I'm taking a quote from somebody else who said... what's a researcher's favorite radio station? it's WIFM... [meaning] "What's in It For Me?" One researcher mentioned [this] back on a call early this morning, so that's part of what we're hoping to address.

[21:01]

Yvonne Ivey

First, would it be helpful for us to jump into OpenCore?

Brooks Hanson

That's what I was thinking. And then we can come back to some of the society opportunities later. This gives a little bit of context, but I think we can do that later too, and I think that gets started getting at questions. So, if you just go down to and yeah... this is OpenCore.

So, the initial plan presented to you I think in spring... and that that we had thought... was so these would be developed by open experts in a fully open process ready by the AGU Fall meeting... started by content development and it was... so this did happen... that it was a content development and sprint in the summer and we got a huge amount of great content around the five Open Science Ethos... data, results, tools, software... We got great content for all of that, but we didn't have the full designs constraints. So, some of that was aligned with what the MVP is envisioned now, some of it was not. **There is an extremely tight schedule for development and we ran into capacity and some other challenges and asked for the volunteers that were provided some compensation, but not the level that we needed to take this fall through to completion and then the transition from and an understanding of that content to an educational framework was also a big lift**, so slightly revised plan. And you know, to be fair, I think given a large range of conversations, this is a... how quickly we're trying to do this and learning as we go. It is a building an airplane while you're flying and changing the design of the airplane while it was flying a little bit, too. So, both of those are happening.

Next slide. So, where we've settled on the requirements through a number of conversations with NASA on this first round of core content, so it's these five modules (which I'll go over in a minute), the initial focus will be on the Earth and Space sciences... in stories and narratives and relevant content. **Admittedly, 80 or 90% of open science content is disciplinary agnostic in a large sense.** There are some special considerations. The earth is being scientist is a little more field based or place based. It's integrating a number of data sets. That's true of a lot of other things... a few other aspects that are Earth and Space Science relevant. Chelle and others mentioned SMD41a yesterday. I think there's supposed to be a hyphen in there, sorry. And the requirements that are in that should also be supported in this. It is designed as an introduction to open science for open science naïve/unaware researchers. **From a laws and regulations point of view... because the focus is supporting NASA's scientists initially and writ large... it's more of a U.S. versus global focus, especially for laws and regulations.**

So, as we all know, the U.S. has some laws and regulations that are a little bit unique in terms of open software, open data, who and others you can collaborate with and so forth. So, there's slightly more emphasis on those than other regulations worldwide in the MVP. And I emphasize this is the very first part and all the global and other aspects can be added later.

A key part is how to get help and engage with communities. Five courses, two and a half hours each... online and in-person. So already that was a challenge because the initial content we got from the sprint, each module took about four or five hours to read. So, there is a lot more information and great content, especially when you get it down to a coursework for... you're having learning exercises and other things like that.

Monica

What did you do with that excess content?

[25:59]

Brooks Hanson

I'll get to that a second. So, researcher focus... and I put in this quote... I added this this morning and put that in, but it really needs to be what is the and I think this is something that was agreed upon by all is... to engage the researchers and to really get at that culture challenge, is really have it focus on *the* value propositions (plural) and they should be their value propositions for the researchers.

It's not just here's a set of practices that are great. It's really why should you what's the advantages both to you and to you... and also, I think researchers do want to contribute to the larger science. So, I was trying to remember the quote from yesterday where it was individual generosity or global generosity. I was trying to remember that, because I thought that was a very good framing of one of the value propositions.

So, Jim, what was it? *Intellectual generosity*. **Intellectual generosity**. And... can we quote you on that or recite that or something? (*Jim says he will share that source*). But there's obviously an impact ease of efficiency and other things like that... that are important.

We talked about badges yesterday and so there is – I can talk further about that – but there is an assessment. There's also a good takeaway that we're including from the course that is... your plan for open science. So that'll be part of what comes out of this. We want to capture that too. It's not just a take away. We want that as part of... that won't be part of the completing. It will be part of the assessment. But what's in it is will not be assessed per se, because there's not a quick way to do that. But so there will be assessment and a plan for open science. And we've moved back to timeline a little bit. Our goal is to have it Ethos ready by the Fall meeting and perhaps one other module, but then the full module minimum because first minimum MVP by mid-April... April 1... I'll talk about the next slide.... and so, Monica, is it getting back to your question was...

Monica

So ... what for... the excess material?

Brooks Hanson

Okay, so great. So, we are working with the creators of that content. In fact, I was just exchanging some emails yesterday with them... to help them post that under a CC license on a repository of their choice. Further development of that... we've had a number of conversations

with the creators of that content, as has NASA, about thinking about how to help provide support to develop that content further, if they so wish...

Monica???

And these... going to be part of the OpenCore stuff?

Brooks Hanson

So, the other discussion that's going on with them right now... **is the right way to credit and attribute that content.** So, it is at least derived from, developed from... with additional material going forward that will be added in, such as Jim's quote... obviously a lot more other stuff like that, that is... organizing, editing, additional content and stories. We've reached out, for example, to Earth Cube, which is a large NSF funded infrastructure. And some of the stories that Chelle was getting... to see what we can bring in from other sources in terms of enriching that in Earth and Space sciences and **some of what is already in that sprint output, which we're calling foundational material.** ... it includes stories and assessments as well. And as we add assessments in, we'll probably pull from there... and if that content grows and develops further, there's the opportunity also to use that as a source. So, the idea was... in going into this... to not recreate things from scratch, but to leverage what The Carpentries have done, what Turing way has done, what others have... faculty courses and things like that... as much as possible that's under a CC license.

Monica

And when you say CC license... do you mean is it going to be CC-BY license?

Brooks Hanson

So, I think they are still figuring that out. *They being the creators?* They have talked between CC-0 and CC-BY. So, I don't think it's on us to impose that on them.

Monica

Yeah. I'm just thinking of... just going back to this idea of badges and getting credit... it would be great to be able to point to... my colleague Daniela... who contributed... so her name...

Brooks Hanson

So, I think... in our thinking about this... this isn't final yet. **We don't see this as an authored product.** You know, it's not going to be a list of that. **In part because I think there's some a little discomfort in all the condensing reorganization that had to be done...** that I think it's hard for people to see we've put this content here now... I want to be an author of this thing, but we absolutely want to recognize all the contributions, including we've already had some fantastic reviewer comments from NASA scientists and from them as well. And we're about to open it up the first module to an open review. So, how do we recognize all of the input that's coming in into this in some kind of fair, transparent, inclusive contributor statement?

Malvika Sharan

Malvika here. I was also one of the subject matter experts. *Thank you.* I want to actually raise a huge concern that this thing was never shared with SMEs... **we were not told what would happen with the content being developed.** We were not told what the process of revising would

look like. And I'm privileged to be sitting here and probably speak on behalf of all SMEs. And I think that was probably not a very right move. Especially in open source, it's everybody who's an SME, they are extremely privileged to be in that position as well. And now that I'm hearing that all the content that has been developed, it's going to be taken without them, which is all right. But that was also not discussed.

Brooks Hanson

So, Malvika, hi yes, and on one of the next slides, you don't have to go to it yet... I have some of the challenges and the steps... if you want to call them that... are lessons learned that that we've had in flying this plane while it's been building. Our hope was initially to have the open review and post that content openly *right* after the sprint. That was one of the adjustments that we made in discussion with NASA... in part, I think there were several reasons for that. One was it wasn't ready to be posted on the NASA GitHub site. And so, there was appearance of endorsement that NASA wasn't ready for and that we weren't ready for. There was also the...

Chelle Gentemann

Brooks, I'm going to just jump in there. But posting on the NASA GitHub was never really about endorsement. We endorse what the community created. It was that once it goes on the NASA GitHub, it's very difficult to make pull requests. It's not a collaborative environment. So, we wanted to be able to link to... an openly developed repository, where the subject matter experts and the module leads had control and ownership over it. It wasn't that... it was just the pull request thing. We don't have admin.

Speaker 3??

One quick question... why is it difficult? Just because it's a NASA repository and there are guidelines?

Chelle Gentemann

Specifically, because it's in NASA's GitHub... so it's only NASA employees that can accept pull requests.

[33:57]

Yvonne Ivey

There's a specific moderator role that we have to put in a special request for. So, even Cyndi and Isabella, who are a part of our core team, don't have access as a moderator. So, Chelle kind of alluded to this yesterday... but the GitHub repo is actually managed by the Chief Information Office. And so, anything we do, we have to follow and kind of go over that process. So, we've been evaluating how open *that* is. We don't even have full maintainer/moderator rights. So, we've been really trying to figure out how to get through a lot of the red tape when it comes to this repo.

Fernando

I'm on a GitHub pages link just now with an example that... you couldn't you can do that. You could do the other part... you couldn't fix to GitHub pages rendered because you don't have the controls.

Chelle Gentemann

Yeah. So, I had to email someone and we're still thinking maybe it's okay, but we'll figure out if they'll enable that for me. But the specific thing is... NASA always wanted this to be fully open and developed... and it's easy for us to link to that from our GitHub repo. It was just that we couldn't post... because of that.

[35:15]

Malvika Sharan

I just want to also say... I'm not blaming anybody, but I'm just like sharing my lived experience and concern. I think what my worry from this whole situation is... that you did *everything* correct. You got this *hugely* diverse group of people together with the amount of experience that they have from their environment. **We were made to believe that those lived experience count, right?** And I'm not saying that it doesn't count. Again, like I know you all and I love you all and I know you have really good intentions, but I feel that in this process people get hurt because it's happening openly and **we just need to be aware that this doesn't happen next time. We need to be aware that there are guidelines, there are expectations set from the beginning that people... if they spend a week of their life building something, they're rewarded for that not just in terms of monetary sense, but... intellectual generosity that they have shown.** Can we respect that?

Could they point to the outcome that comes out in NASA's website? Would they recognize what they have done if we take the whole material and revise it in a way, in ways *we* want to tell, not *they* want to do... of course they understand this material is targeted to the U.S. citizens.

However, you brought these international people. You should have told them that they are constrained. And here with these constraints we are leveling you up by giving you that knowledge about U.S. policies and regulation. And I know that this is beginning right. We're going to probably do some great things in the next four years. And I just want to make sure this doesn't happen in the future. And again, I'm not telling people... respect. I know you all worry and concern. You have concerns about this, too.

Brooks Hanson

So absolutely... could have been better communication. And so, I do think we collectively... we have learned greatly from this experience. Some of our communications are still trying to learn further from this experience. So, thank you for those comments.

I will say... that one of the challenges is that some of what is on this slide we have come in to constrain the modules going forward... wasn't thought about at the beginning of the process, so I don't think we thought about the U.S. constraint versus the global constraint, initially. So, we obviously should have communicated better as soon as that constraint came forward. **And in thinking about how do we take in a huge amount of content into something that's viable and educational?** And I think the understanding, including by our team, of what it would take to get from initial content to educational design... we're learning. So, thank you, Malvika and others and... you're not the only one we've heard that from and we are doing our best to internalize it. I can't promise we won't have missteps forward, but I think we have a... we've heard it and we'll do our best.

Fernando Perez

Fernando Perez from UC Berkeley. I wasn't obviously part... I was not one of the SMEs. I'm just trying to understand...when... between kind of the framing that Malvika's presenting from your experience and the comment you made earlier, Brooks, about the fact that you thought it was it was the SMEs and maybe I misunderstood you, but I understood... you say that it was the SMEs were not comfortable with their authorship being represented there, but I think Malvika just said a minute ago say that actually it's important for the SMEs to see their authorship represented. And I'd like to understand, maybe I'm mishearing you or if you can clarify that.

[39:14]

Brooks Hanson

So, there's a lot of... how to represent something that the SMEs are comfortable with. I mean, the final product is... we don't have a final product yet. So, it's quite possible that... a contribution, we'll say yes... in two months. This is great. I don't know. **The concern we've heard now, recently, is that the state of this now is different enough from the foundational material, both in terms of what was removed and how it was organized and reorganized and edited that there's a little discomfort with 'I'm an author on this.'** So, because.... so X topic was heavily emphasized in the foundational material. Some of the global stuff was heavily emphasized in the foundation. Material isn't as emphasized in the MVP.

Monica

But couldn't just give them the option to be an author?

Brooks Hanson

Absolutely.

Malvika Sharan

Sorry, probably give more chance to others. **I think we need to practice what we are teaching. If we want people to understand version control reproducibility, understanding people's diversity and focusing on equity, we need to practice that.** We need to project that in the best way possible. And I understand that's a state of concern. But we have all kinds of version control possibility, right. It's not really about... is the final outcome showing my contribution, but is there a history to track what people have done great and... there is no way you can go back to that material and say this is what my record wrote, that this is what Malvika wrote, and this is what of this is what I wrote, right? There's no way for people to actually do that.

So, although we are doing this collaborative work, there's also sense of personal identity and people's contribution. So, I'm not saying that your final outcome needs to have that, but because all of these people were brought in to share their knowledge and they did share that knowledge... they should have a way to go back and for their sake, recognize that this is what I have done and we'll have to probably figure out what the solution could be. For example, we can set up an independent GitHub repository, which I'm sure OpenCore leads are thinking about and get all of as a means to write their version because then you have it all up there. People can go back and see it. There are lots of ways to recognize that in terms of... there are all contributors for acknowledgment sheets and I think in a very blunt way... I really wouldn't care what happens to the material from now on, but I do care what material we have right now and go back and,

reverse engineer and see how we can actually make that happen. We do have collective experience from open source doing that.

Brooks Hanson

So, we are in conversations on that. So, our thought was on author contribution, whatever we want to call this that... our communication with the SMEs right now is please help us on that, please... let us know what you want and what the best process is.

Malvika

We did not know. It was not communicated.

Yvonne Ivey

I'm sorry. We have...I want to engage the folks who are online and Sara has her hand raised. I might be doing you a moment. Sara, can you unmute? Sara, I think I unmuted you.

Fernando

Pressing on it. Are participants allowed to unmute or...?

Yvonne Ivey

We gave them the option. While Sara is unmuting, we've had several things in the chat and so I just want to hit on them. One of the first comments were from Mercury. I'm sorry, if I mispronounced your name. I will scroll up for the folks in the room slowly. Okay. *Reading from chat*: 'It looks like a grassroots strategy...what is the plan to enroll the university institutional leaders in the creation and enforcement of open science policies?'

Brooks Hanson

So, I will get to that in a later slide.

Isabella Martinez

And I also think that was a reference to SPD...

Chelle Gentemann

Yeah, I think, I think that was a different topic.

[44:06]

Brooks Hanson

Yeah. So, I'll get to that in our outreach engagement.

Yvonne Ivey

Okay. A comment [in the chat] from Brian agreeing to CC.

Brooks Hanson

Yeah. I think that's getting back to the question that...

Yvonne Ivey

I recognize the time span. I want to make sure folks online are also a part of the conversation. Bob reference is 'it's good to make sure'...*I'm assuming you're referencing subject matter experts...* 'don't feel tokenized.'

[44:45]

Sara

So, I just [want to] thank you so much for giving me space. And I just want to voice and help answer some of the questions that came from the panelists... as a module lead, especially for Open Data. So, and I echo everything that Malvika has said... GitHub is not the Holy Grail or the only way of doing it openly. We have been working on Google Docs...but a lack of transparency has led to a lot of confusion and the second thing is the why and I can speak from on my behalf and the SME's behalf... **why we refuse to have our names associated with the content that doesn't represent us is because we were not involved in its creation**. And unlike Ethos that was in a fluke, was allowed to be seen by the SMEs, Open Data was not. So, neither us or the SMEs know how it would look like at all until it's out there with the community. So, it's a little bit hard to go through this process and say, yes, we've seen that Ethos has been completed. **How is Open Data going to be handled? Does this represent what we worked on or not?** And that does not mean that we did not want our names associated for any reason other than **we want to have our voices truly heard and not just tokenized by using our names on it**.

Brooks Hanson

Sara, our intent is... just to be clear... is to share all the modules back with the leads.

Sara

I was given a clear 'no' and the content would be only shared with the SMEs after the community... after it's out in the public. So that's another thing. Right, okay, so going forward... **that's why there is such an aversion between the Foundational and OpenCore stuff**. And we hope that in one way or the other we continue to influence and get our voices in there, as it's planned. So, that's just to clarify the situation and a bit of the confusion that's happening.

Brooks Hanson

Thanks, Sara.

Isabella Martinez

I believe Jim raised a hand.

Jim Colliander

Yeah. So, **I think all of us are very concerned. This conversation feels awkward. I hear voices that sound scared from people that are out of the traditionally privileged groups**. I perceive in Brooks, a concern around institutional protection, a desire to make sure that AGU is a fair dealer in here and as a TOPS panelist, I'm extremely concerned about the initial condition of what forms the basis of the core metrics of success. 20,000 people are supposed get badges based on this material, and some of the pioneering content creators that led to this are upset about the circumstances.

This is a fundamental risk to TOPS, and I strongly suggest that the NASA leadership take this advice from me now. **Fix this and I suggest that we don't fix it today in the panel, but we set up some sort of a forum that enables these content creators who feel like they're getting tokenized or dismissed... and AGU... to come to terms.** Right now, I think the circumstances are the voices have expressed that there's some concern and I'm hearing it... I think everyone's hearing it, but everyone's a little defensive about whatever they're doing. But we have to get through this. **Open science is awkward sometimes. Let's find a constructive way to move through the awkwardness so that we're all happy, or at least at consensus afterwards.** Malvika, does this proposal sound like it would work well with you to make sure that there is a different forum where this can be explored? Or is this the forum where you think it should be explored?

Malvika

I am in agreement with you. We're just being human in the public, right. It's tough and I see it's tough for Brooks, it's tough for the whole team. And thank you, Sara, for speaking up. I don't want to make you speak up again, but can you can you probably weigh in? Do you think a public forum... not public forum, sorry... I think this needs to be a bit more closed forum discussion with the SMEs and module leads. Sara, do you agree with Jim's suggestion?

Sara

I think it would be most welcome and having all the voices of those who contributed to be heard and **having clarity on what the process is and what is expected out of us, that would help — having examples of what product that people want at the end and giving us a chance to really work on that.**

Fernando Perez

This is Fernando from Berkeley. And yeah, as I said, I was not an SME, I am equally concerned about this. I wanna... Sara just used the word 'process' and I think it's important to keep in mind one thing that I think is important... and I don't want this Brooks, to sound in any way, shape or form like an attack. I realize that right now this a difficult situation for your team.

But I think it's important to emphasize that open science is a process, not a product. Right. And when it seems to me that part of the issue here is precisely that the offer... and there might have been some misunderstandings.... I don't know about the communication, but that materials would be shared with the SMEs at the end. That is a product perspective, if I hear it correctly, or that they would be shared it at some point. It seems to me like part of the issue coming from the voices that I hear in the room of the SMEs is one of **participation in a process**. And so, I would want to encourage that in whatever steps are taken next to help improve the situation, to move forward... I think all of us here are aligned with we *want* this to be a success that transforms science.

And I've been doing this for 20 years... I've run through my fair share of rough patches. They're difficult, they're uncomfortable. We work through them in good faith. And I think everyone here is acting in good faith. I want to believe that. So, one more challenging step is one that we can work through as a team. But the thing that has always — the places where I have seen successes and the places where I have seen failures always seem to be **strongly correlated with how well**

structured the processes is for participation. All of us are capable of accepting outcomes that are not quite the ones we wanted, but we tend to accept those much better when we feel that we were part of the process than we were not... and so I want to encourage that... we imagine what the next stage of this would be and whatever form of suggestions may come that make those **voices heard in the processes and not just in the outcomes**.

Yvonne Ivey

So, thank you for that, Fernando. Pen, I recognize your hand is raised. Do you mind if we take a quick five-minute break before we talk to you?

Pen-Yuan Hsing

That sounds good. Thank you.

Yvonne Ivey

Okay, five-minute break, y'all.

Participants return from the break.

Pen-Yuan Hsing

Oh, okay. Thanks. Yeah, I just have a quick suggestion... that I had as I was listening to everyone. I think acknowledging that what we're talking about is a bit uncomfortable. I think it is actually a very valuable process, right. And I think we acknowledge that we are not the only group who is struggling with this. This is something that happens in open science, in different places, different contexts and different forms. As we continue to struggle with this, you know, coming months... and hopefully find a good solution, we will learn something and we will learn some valuable lessons. So, in the spirit of what we're actually trying to create with this outreach and education material... **I think it would be very valuable us to not only record this process but actually write it up as something to incorporate into OpenCore and around open science education**. Because there's so much material out there right now, right, about the tools that we can use to do open science where you should publish and what those outputs should look like. But again, going back to the point earlier about how open science is the process... what we're talking about right now *is* one of those really important processes. And what we learned, I think, would be such a valuable part of what can go into these courses. I don't know if it will fit in the MVP that's on the slide that I'm talking about right now. But the slide does say that we should focus on good practices. And I think this is a very important process that can be part of the quote practices. So, I think it's worth, **not only learning lessons from this, but actually incorporating those lessons into what we write up for these courses**. That's just my quick comment and observation. I'm curious to see what you all think about that. Thanks.

Chelle Gentemann

I want to address how much we want this conversation, which is sort of uncomfortable... and I really want to recognize what Jim said about **the power dynamics in the room**. So, Pen, while I agree with you... **there have been some allegations of code of conduct violations and misconduct that are part of this that maybe aren't part of the public conversation**. So, it may not be a safe space for that conversation. And I want to recognize that. So, asking NASA, AGU, and the module leads to come back to the table which has put in the chat... we already

tried in private and we weren't able to really resolve this. And I honestly don't know... I really want to find a path forward.

And so maybe a next step is instead of... I want to be really cognizant of people being hurt here... is that maybe the next step is not to all come together, but to **get an actual facilitator** and talk with... I agree, Pen, that there's *so much* to be learned from this experience and that we should try to *later* in a safe space, talk about this and figure out how we can write this up as a learning experience. Because this is not... I don't think this is anybody's first rodeo that this has happened to... this happens in *every* project I've been part of at one point or another. So, **let's try to take a little time, find some safe spaces to discuss this and use a facilitator to maybe come to a path forward that would be, not just acceptable, but actually, hopefully bring us back to being a team.**

Yvonne Ivey

But also, we want to recognize that we want a sense of mutual recognition and understanding of the pathway forward. And I think Malvika said this perfectly earlier... that *this* forum is not that space. And so... Monica, I know you had your hand raised...but I would like to move the conversation forward.

Monica

I was just going to suggest that to follow up with me... this is Monica. We had something similar happen to another event that I attended where we were trying to get some language about systems of oppression and white supremacy. And there was conflict in the room and we did use a facilitator to have a conversation afterwards. And so, **follow-up with me and I can give you the name of the facilitator that helped with that process.** *Thank you very much.*

Yvonne Ivey

Alright, let's... Pen, you have your hand raised?

Pen-Yuan

Oh, yes. Thank you, yeah, it's Pen. Yeah, just really quick... I wasn't implying that what I was suggesting should be something done **right now, right?** And that's part of why I was saying it might not even be part of this MVP. **I think it would be useful to have some distance after we've gone through this process... distance in terms of time.** And if people are willing, *then* we can reflect on what we've learned and that lesson will be really useful, but certainly not for something we do immediately. Also, I do agree having a facilitator for this would be good. Thank you.

Yvonne Ivey

Thanks, y'all.

Question/Speaker ??

I just have a really quick question and this is maybe going in the theme of moving the conversation in a different direction. **How does the course materials not being made available until after the start of the Year of Open Science affect the launch in January?** I feel like... the Year of Open Science, but we might not have the course available to teach you yet.

[59:40]

Brooks Hanson

So, that's the full online version. So, I think the goal at the AGU Fall meeting is to teach it in person. So, it's... at least that's the current plan right now...so that the full courses aren't available, that the current plan is to teach... at least the Ethos module and other things in person, so that you're less dependent on the full online thing being available. But because the in-person experience can be different from that...based on it... but different.

Yvonne Ivey

So maybe this is a great segway into your slide.

Brooks Hanson

So just... I think part of the challenge and I appreciate everything Yo and others have and Sara that you have said and Malvika, thank you. And I completely agree with all of it. And I want Monica and thank you for the suggestion of a facilitator. I think I got that right. And Monica, your second I think that would be welcome on all of our sides.

One of the challenges is, as I said, **like that MVP... we in hindsight absolutely should have had that envisioned at the start of the project.** It came through many of those kinds of requirements or whatever we call it... MVP objectives... were developed even not all at the same time after the start of the project. So, I think things like that have exacerbated expectations and communications and made people in part feel like they provided input that wasn't useful... or as useful as it could have been. So, in terms of valuing people's time... so the current... sorry, this is a little tight.

So, as I mentioned, we had this **foundational material workshop sprint** and there was a lot of material produced in five days or three days and then refined. There's been... in that, as we mentioned, that's been taken forward. The process we've agreed upon with NASA is they would have a first small review of each module. So, this is the timeline for the Ethos module. This is the current plan. Happy to have input on revising it... and that's between Chelle and Steve. Then there's a second review that's just been completed for Ethos that Malvika participated in and others have facilitated with SMEs and some NASA's subject matter experts.

And we've just resolved those review comments and those are fantastic. They've led to a significant in all of our reviews – a significant improvement, and I think also in the expectation... so that review was on the base content not the assessment material which we're adding, not some of the stories and enrichments and things like that. Also, kind of managing expectations of what we're asking for people and what a challenge has been envisioning what the finished project/product would look like as it moves through the process.

That stuff is being... Sara, just to be clear, this is intended for *all* the modules. So, absolutely our intent, at least on this current model was that all the SMEs would have a chance to provide that review of data results, etc., etc.. So, I'm sorry if there was a misunderstanding or miscommunication on that... the assessments and others would be added and then we would

have a period of open review that would be migrated to GitHub... to the learning platform GitHub. So, not the NASA one, where a fully open review would be possible.

And one of the challenges also I think I have this on the other slide, but you don't have to show that now. **We still don't have any review from the 'naïve' Open science researchers.** So, is this resonating? Do the assessments work, other things like that. We don't have that review yet. Do you want to ask a question? Or do you want me to finish? I can go either way.

So that's at the end of the top arrow. So, then there is an open review of the learning module, which it's going to be fully open at that point. While we're finalizing graphics, the in-person training would happen and then there's a lot of further refinement based on feedback from that early testing that goes into further improvement to an MVP. And then there's a whole development process after that. So that is our... **this is replicated for all the modules, pushed back about three weeks in the sequence.** So that's the current plan. Obviously, here are some of the learning challenges I put up anticipating this conversation... there others are too. You want to go back to which slide is better for the discussion.

Question/ Speaker ??

Take care from... just wanted to ask about the thought process behind and again, I don't want to rehash conversations that folks might have already had, but I wasn't an SME, so I don't have the full perspective on the course development process. **But why not make the materials and the deliverables and the review process open by default to begin with?** Like, why not? Is there a logistical benefit of not having any GitHub repository somewhere that everybody can see and they can pull it and have that **review process be fully transparent** instead of the existing process? And I also think just again, **from a transparency standpoint, it would be interesting to see... what/who is involved in these different review processes, what are the deliverables that go from stage to stage?** I think they would all be helpful from a technical point of view as well.

Brooks???

Chelle, do you want to answer the question about open review from the beginning... or for me to try to do that...

Question/Speaker ??

And again, from my perspective, thinking about open science...

Brooks Hanson

So I think it is... and the challenge we've had is anticipating the final product piece of it vis a vis... I guess we made a decision... we collectively to move towards more educational bit... that given the tight timeline... the really valuable feedback from an open point of view would be having a better sense of what the educational material look like versus the foundational material.

[1:07:11]

Chelle Gentemann

I want to say that during... there was a small period with a public/open review and what ended up happening was I got complaints because people were making reviewer comments and they

weren't getting any feedback. And we decided, I think, that we weren't ready to *handle* an open review. So, it wasn't actually about not wanting feedback or not wanting to hear comments... it was about our *ability* to digest that. But that was six weeks ago or more. And the idea was that... TOPS as a mission... we want as much of everything done in the open, done publicly, shared openly with CC-0 or CC-BY license.

We would like authors to get credit... and we would like this to be a fully open process because... I don't think that if we are trying to create... we're trying to create an open science curriculum that's going to resonate with 20,000 people. I don't think... I think... that the best way to do that is to *include* as many voices and opinions in that feedback. And I've often... my science team... you argue over an idea and then you come together and it's part of us building community. And it's messy a little bit sometimes, but it actually makes us all stronger. We have to do that in a healthy, safe, respectful environment.

Fernando Perez

It's Fernando from Berkeley. I've been thinking and... both about this conversation, about something that I've seen actually for the last maybe ten years plus... where I think this is an example of an issue that I just want to put here for the whole team, for all of the sub teams to reflect on them. And it goes to this specific process of **bringing many voices**. And I don't exactly know what the answer to this is... but what my observation is that... the dynamics of public collaborative, what I would call **co-creation**, right, of open source software entities, is very subtle and difficult... and even though I've been in the thick of both... very difficult to understand differently from the dynamics of the co-creation of what, let's call it, content... author content. There is something different about these two things. It's far more challenging to co-create in a team... content that I would say has a narrative voice and where the sense of authorship is very strong and there is a very strong intent of authorship... it's far more difficult and I think *I* have fallen into that difficult situation where... the practices, the cultural practices and the dynamics that I know work really, really well... and that I use fluidly and that I expect to work really well in the process of creating software collaboratively... fall... begin to like... the gears begin to grind badly and I'm not sure the answer to this is, but I think there's an element of that in here. **There's a tension between an intent of authorship**.

I was thinking about the term that has been used often in this discussion. The term 'review'... review is... here is something for you to give me input on. We tend in software development to do things in... the review is a very ongoing... it's kind of like micro review, right? There's a small pull request that makes a change here and here. And you know, at some point there's a little bit of review and feedback, but it is *so* interwoven in the process that it doesn't feel like review... and come back. It feels just it's happening together, right. And yet we observe that it's difficult to bring that dynamic into the creation of content. And so, I'm just putting that out, so that we may need to realize that some of these practices of the good things – both the tooling and the cultural behavior that we have in open-source software creation – we may learn lessons from them – but to the creation of authored content, maybe not everything translates quite the same. And so maybe we need to think carefully about *how* do we set up a process and some of it may be planning, expectations setting, who will be on that, what is the role of each? And if that process and those expectations are set upfront correctly... and I'm not blaming anyone... and this is really hard.

I remember conversations actually with Greg Wilson... probably 14 years ago... **about how hard it is to get people to share**. And Greg had great analogies about musical sharing and why... I remember discussions with Greg literally from founder of The Carpentries for those who don't know him. Right, about how hard this is in some spaces. **So, I don't have an answer, but I wanted to open that line where... maybe some of this tension is because we are attempting to translate something that *doesn't* quite translate and maybe we can engineer it a little bit differently.** So that's what I want to put out.

Jim Colliander

Just to build on what Fernando said. This is Jim Colliander. So, I'm inspired by conversations that I've had with Yuvi Panda and I want to share something that I got from him. So, I think we're built... we're dancing around a concept that is not crystallized... which is the right to participate. **What does it mean to participate in an open science process? And if a person does participate, what is their attribution? What's their role? How do we remember their contribution or include them?** And there may be some sort of an open science bill of rights or a constitution for what it means to be an open scientist and... so they feel like their rights were violated, but the rights aren't easily articulated. So that's one concept.

The second concept builds on what Fernando said... Wikipedia seems to have figured this out. Now, the content that they're creating is an encyclopedia entry, which is less associated with an individual author. But a user of Wikipedia is not called a user. If you log into Wikipedia, you're instantly given the title, not reviewer... you're an editor. Everybody's an editor on Wikipedia. So, there's a certain role that comes with the title. **And your role is not just creator of content, but rather an editor and a creator at the same time.** So, there may be some language around the... *subject matter experts*. So that elevates me to think that I'm an expert and therefore I want that laudatory role of expertise. But if you call me an editor... I have some authority, but I don't get the byline as an editor necessarily unless I'm writing an editorial. **So, there might be some changes in role definition and rights of participants here to explore.**

Malvika

I just want to include... I'm going to bring the experience from the Turing Way, which is a content creation with people. **And I think the role is very, very important.** And also, **people need to know what they're doing** because if there is... for now, I would say... even if we forget about all the content... we know what chapters, for example, we want, right and... if we want to continue with the SMEs or even bring new people into that, **we need to have them identify what they're going to work on** and get them to work together.

And then again, you know, talking about participatory process and co-creation... people don't expect what they wrote in the first draft will be what they'll see in the last draft right. But then in that process, what they're doing, they feel like they have a say, an involvement in doing that. In the next slide, I saw something that I wanted to actually bring up... is what Carpentries has done very brilliantly, is that they involve learners into getting a pull request on their repository and it gives the learner a little bit of like, oh, I actually know enough now to do the change. **And they get to have that participatory process built in and they get some buy-in into the material that they're going to eventually take and learn to teach other people.**

And another thing Carpentries does really well, and sorry SherAron.... I'm speaking quite a lot for Carpentry. There's something called RFC, [which means] **Request for Comment**, which is which is very different from review. You say it's open for three weeks, four weeks. We are going to respond to you... but we're going to open it for people to leave their comments. And there's no responsibility that you would address them within that period. And then you say, we're going to take another three months to address all the comments that came in. Let's see where it gets integrated. And then you go through that process a few times.... version one, version two or three and they give do that point like vertical grading, which I do lot in my work. And I think that could be revised in some ways.

Yvonne Ivey

Folks online... any... comments?

Monica

I just want to add to the Wikipedia comment... is that they *do* struggle though with this problem that editors still have power to decide whether a contribution is included or not. And I know that there's been certain communities who – like a colleague of mine – has been trying to get an entry for someone at UNESCO for a really long time, and it just keeps getting denied... Sharmila. And either they don't have the notoriety or... these sort of decisions and... why there's been sort of an upswell in trying to get more women into Wikipedia as well, especially women of color, right. So, you know, it's interesting. It's not a new power. It's just that's power systems. And I'm not sure that we're going to be able to necessarily solve it. **But the first thing is to recognize that there is a power imbalance here**, because ultimately AGU has the ultimate decision on what's included. **But I think the transparency would help**... I know what the Wikipedia sense would be great if we knew 'what's the problem and how could we fix it?'... rather than saying well, 'it's been deleted because'....

Jim Colliander

I think... I've elevated Wikipedia as having solved all these problems... and I don't think they've solved all the problems. I can see that. But I do think that the content of Wikipedia being so massive and the debates take place... **there's something to learn there. For sure. There is a collaborative effort at creating content that is not typically associated with a single author.** So, there might be some lessons there.

Monica

For sure. And version controls....

Chelle Gentemann

I'm going to jump in on one comment. Kevin and I have been talking about asking the panel for this advice... **so NASA has the final say, not AGU... and we will determine what is the OpenCore curriculum.** Right now, we have a *difficulty* as an agency. There's two products that are at this point... I don't want to say similar, but they're not similar, but they're not different. They're... an introduction to open science. Two of the modules have been sort of worked on extensively by AGU. **But a lot of the structure has been changed**... but a lot of it is in essence similar to what the SMEs created. But there's differences. But it's not like an apple and an

orange. It's like an orange in a tanglo???. Okay, I'm going to get this wrong. So, I would like to ask the panel... we have a situation where we have things diverging and I don't... how do we handle this?

[1:19:44]

Yvonne Ivey

But also, looking at the timeline... one of the things we recognize and as Chelle said, you know, we're not reinventing the wheel here... folks have been developing curriculum forever. Looking at our timeline and sort of the process that has been laid out by AGU... **are we missing things? Are there things that we should pause and re-evaluate? Are there things in this timeline that gives you pause?** I think Logan hit this earlier when he was talking about... put it out there, open it up, have everyone give you comments... there's this really great TikTok and I'll share it late, where it's... if you want to do something fast or there's like three things: you do it fast, you do it well... or you actually get the right materials.

And it's... we have the process and we have... as Chelle mentioned, our Chief Science Data Office's blessing to do this right. And if we need to pause and evaluate and actually make sure that we're giving our best...

Chelle Gentemann

We want to do that. And if the answer is we need to stop and work on governance, roles and responsibilities... I would like the panelists to weigh in... because this bifurcation is very difficult for us to navigate because... it's not... that's not a winning strategy, unless we want to have two products that we just choose at the end, which is another strategy. So, I think Fernando and then Logan...

Fernando Perez

I have a concrete suggestion to make... that is based on an idea that we already shared yesterday then that you need to have the time to do in code... which is this **concept of the right to replicate**. Right. And I would like to see how that fits into this point. And for those online this Fernando Perez from Berkeley, I'm pointing at the end arrow on the slide that's being shared that says 'finalize online'.

I think one: it doesn't fully address the question of that Chelle has just made, but I would want this outcome that AGU is working on, right... to be designed from the get go in a way that embraces this right to replicate in the following sense... that even if AGU deploys it on a specific online platform that is connected with like professional badging and recognition, what not... the way that content is designed and made available hopefully is such that... *any* community in any other location that is not affiliated with AGU... with **absolutely ideally zero or minimal effort, can take and redeploy and reuse that material without it depending on the structure** that happens to be usable by this specific... whichever specific online platform is being used. Right. So that's basically kind of *normal* content that's reusable... that is the analogy that we use in into it to see is... everything that's done will not depend on whether it happens to be at Google or whatever cloud provider, so that... the end user can be empowered to do that on their own terms. If that's encoded in there, it doesn't fully solve this problem of the choice, but I

think it does present **the community version that may not be tied to the online platform** choices of AGU... is a more equal entry point.

Speaker???

So, I think... that came up yesterday in Jim's... So, I think that's absolutely critical...

Chelle Gentemann

So, I want to note that Daniela made a comment as one of the SMEs... **'I was never expecting the content I contribute to over the course of a few days to be kept verbatim but I was expecting editing to happen and then being involved in that process.'**

So again, I think this point is back to defining roles very clearly and Brian then provided a link. Thank you, Brian... to... clearly this is not to lay blame at anyone's feet, but to say this is something that a lot of people have struggled with and it's time for us to struggle with this... I guess now I think there was one more...

Brooks Hanson

Thanks, Daniela. One of the other challenges we've been having is not all the SMEs, but I think several have indicated to us that... **we had a small amount of compensation in the grant, but that some of what we're talking about is an... would be a much additional, a great additional effort and how to actually fairly and respectfully do that... would need to be part of the consideration.**

Monica

This is Monica. I want to ask about... what's the parameters here but with this decision of... what do you do next? And I think it would be helpful for this table to know... **what are the consequences of delaying this... in terms of like delivering at the AGU meeting**... and then potentially **what are the consequences for budgeting** as well to help make this decision... or to help *us* help give you some advice on... what would what would we do if I was the director of this project and what it would never do?

Isabella Martinez

We had a couple of folks raise their hand.

Logan

Yeah, really quickly. I was just going to make the comment that the forking narrative... I actually think is one of the cool things about having an open curriculum... that's a feature to me is not something that's necessarily a problem. I think the challenge is if... and if there's more consensus with the forked version than there is with the original one, then that sort of becomes the new verbatim... main copy of whatever it is. But I also think again, going back, if there can be a way to bridge those back, it's a fork. **So, if it's... actually on GitHub or some other platform, you can actually bring the two things back together, which I think is really cool.** So, I wanted to just make that comment... that the fact that it can be forked to begin with is good and it should continue to be able to be forked so that people who want to build off of this... we talked at one of the initial discussions... we as part of this curriculum don't want to tell people what to think about open science. **This is about bringing people's voices in.** So, it sounds

like... by almost not giving people the ability to fork and to create their own version and change things... we would be doing that. We would be saying 'this is open science'. And if this isn't your version of open science, then you're not part of this ecosystem.

SherAaron Hurt

SherAaron with The Carpentries... so full disclaimer, curriculum development, not my forte. So, I've been able to just sit back and listen. And again, as I spoke yesterday... I bring the lens of the human impact... and knowing that this is our first time through and listening to what Yvonne mentioned... getting this thing started, the three things...

That we've come to a place where we realize if we don't have... I mean, like, yes, we have this timeline, but if we're realizing there are some issues and we there's not this... timeline that we have to go for and we're hearing the concerns. I think we're at a place now. We've heard Brooks say we didn't think about this before, but guess what? We're thinking about it right now. So, if these were the things that... we didn't think about, but now we have the capacity to think about it. **I think that it would be best for us to take a pause and say, okay, knowing what we know now, okay, what do we need to consider?**

It goes also back to yesterday when we talked about... **what are our goals, what is the outline?** Again, we are jumping into this, not knowing what the unknowns are. And we're discovering as we go. But now that we've have... we've gotten off these we got a taste of the what our appetite now we can say, okay, now that I know a little something, we probably need to put these things in place. And I think that is considering what Monica stated.... If we were to have to take a pause, what are those things that we need to think about? But I do think that because this is the first time... we have the capacity to say, okay, let's produce something, let's build something, **let's do it right the first time if we can.** Most time we're up against this time frame to say, oh, gosh, we don't have time to sit back and think about it. And in The Carpentries we have this rule... we two-X everything, and now we're learning, we need to three-X everything.

But also, that we have when we do projects as planned pilot pursuits.... that **planning phase is going to take a little bit longer.** And again, I've stated we've jumped into this, but I really do think that **because this is the first time we've had this tension and there's this concern... I think there's a lot on the table for us to take a step back and just talk about this.** And whether it needs to be an open setting or a private setting. I do think that we need to take that time to discuss this stuff.

Isabella Martinez

Pen is next.

[1:29:32]

Pen-Yuan

Hi, it's Pen, thank you. Yeah, I just like to follow on that comment and say, I agree. I think it's worth taking our time right now. But that brings me to a few points I wrote down as all of you were talking... and the first of which is... this timeline that I see on my screen right now and two points about that.

Number one, again, I think it's worth taking the time right now to figure out these really important things we're talking about today. But the other point in this timeline that I see is that... just before the last one... the second to last one is called in-person teaching... **how much planning has there been on getting people ready to conduct the trainings... training the trainers?** Do we have people ready to go who are ready to do that? How much time would it take to get people ready to lead the trainings? So that's my other question about the timeline.

And on a higher level, again, my question is... right now it ends in Q1-2023 (Quarter 1 – 2023), but if we were to adjust the timeline, such as moving things back... back as in later, **what are we aiming for in year five?** And how much would changing this schedule *now* affect what happens in year five, right? So, I guess my question about the timeline is... **what are some of our constraints in terms of how much we can adjust this timeline and do we have to work back from that?** Okay. So that's the timeline.

And just a couple other really quick things. The other quick thing is that... this is something I've been thinking about this entire morning and I'm really glad Fernando brought it up. I think it was Fernando who made a point... about the fact that it's really important to create this material so that it can – not only be replicated by others... but be reused and adapted by them... in different ways and make changes so that it can be applied to a different discipline, for instance.

I want to bring this up because so just to add to what he said, a really important thing is... you mentioned earlier **how to do assessments**. And I think when we assess what comes out of this, a very useful success criteria or a success metric would be... **whether other people have successfully adapted this material to say a different discipline than Earth and Space sciences**. So, it could be a binary kind of metric, whether it has been adapted or it can be more quantitative... maybe how many times it has to be adapted to different contexts. I don't know something to think about, but I just want to make the point that... using the fact that on whether it *has* been adapted and changed is an important success metric... and to achieve that... **I think it's important for the raw materials to be published as much as possible rather than just the rendered outcome.**

So rather than going to a deployed website where you see the end rendered result with a CC-BY license or whatever slapped on it... we should step back from that goal as much as possible to the source. It's the source code, so to speak. We were talking about the end of yesterday of converting what we have from the GitHub repository right now to a Jupyter book format. So better than having the Jupyter book output accessible, we should go back as much as possible to the source... someone could access... I don't know what it's going to be for.. whether it's the markdown files, you know, like images and videos or whatever, **make as much of the raw material accessible as possible.**

And lastly, I really love Yo's point about intellectual generosity and the fact that you will incorporate that into this material. Sorry, I haven't had a chance to read that amazing reference they linked to yet, but I think it is one side of a coin; the other side of which is what I call **intellectual humility**. But that's not in the sense of accepting that you could be wrong about something, but it's recognizing the limits of... what the expansiveness of your ignorance and how much of what *you* are putting out there is actually based on your entire lifetime of learning

from what other people have generously provided. So, it's not just emphasizing *you* should be generous and give what you produce, but also recognizing... how *little* what you have produced compares to the extraordinary amount that you're building on that other people have shared with you. And that's the **intellectual humility** that I think is also very important. **And this humility and generosity are two sides of the same coin.** So, there's a lot of different points, but I've been writing them throughout this morning. So hopefully that's acceptable. Thank you.

Isabella Martinez

Thank you so much. You posed very similar questions to what Monica had. So, I'm going to read what Sara and Yo have put in the chat. I think we'll go back to Monica's question, let Chelle answer, and then Brooks. And then I have on the speaker list: Jim and then Malvika.

So, Sara wrote.... this is Sara's chat comment:

'One thing to consider here, **whose voice weighs more on terms of what goes into the content: AGU or the SMEs?** This has been a clear power struggle. We were told that the content written by us will be copy edited and parts of it chosen. But what happened was that some modules were sent to the drawing board to start again from scratch because it was not what they expected. **So, my question is... who decides what makes it and what doesn't?** This speaks to the tokenism aspect.'

Yo's comment:

'I'll just add... module leads are highly experienced community managers. We do know how to run community driven content. It's our bread and butter. But we need resources to be able to support time if we want to continue with the diverse team.'

Thank you both for adding your comments and for being here today. Monica?

Monica

Yeah so, **it sounds like we're converging to where we probably need to take a step back and reconsider.** And so, if you were going to go down that path... what are considerations that would need to be made? Like one that definitely pops up is... you probably have a big section at AGU that you would need to fill. [There are] probably ways that you could ask... people like Open Life Sciences or pre-review or so many other organizations that could come and teach built material. I'm just saying sort of potentially, if in this scenario where if you decide... I think we need to step back and reevaluate and push these deadlines... so maybe we could help you with that.

Brooks Hanson

We haven't advertised the workshop.

Monica

You haven't advertised the workshops. Okay, so you could... do something else with that time. So, I just... I'm wondering... what are the consequences of... deciding? And it seems like that is sort of the advice that we're hearing at this table and online... **is that you need to take some time to reconsider how you will move forward.**

[Are] there also implications... budgetary implications... we'll have to potentially [pay] people for this extra time? That wasn't built into the timeline. And so, I'd love to hear what the consequences are and if maybe there's even a way for this community to help you.

[1:37:23]

Chelle Gentemann

I'll do the timeline, because that, I think, is a little bit easier. We have a funding announcement, TOPST, that is currently open... almost all of the asks in that funding announcement... that maybe the first one, which is discipline specific extension. So, it's showcase scientific notebooks... but the next two are to run in person workshops at summer schools and to do virtual cohorts. And the concept was... is that at these meetings, where these workshops would be held... people would be taught Ethos, the first module, and then signed up into these virtual cohorts. If they wanted to do it, they could do it either independently online. If they wanted support, they could do it through a virtual cohort.

So having those available... that's why we picked the April date, that can probably be pushed 30 days, maybe. But that's what's driving that. That said, what we need on that date... is not this static perfect open science. We fully expect this to be iterative and... we don't expect it to change massively, but it's going to continue developing.

That's what we want... is for it to continue developing. So, it's October 6th – April is six months away. We have quite a bit of time actually to do... if we engage with professional online course developers. This is actually a totally reasonable amount of time to do an online course... is my understanding, having talked to a number of... course-development experts.

But it's not... we're not also asking for The Sun and the Moon or a full semester long course... it's a two-and-a-half-hour module and maybe we can stagger when those are due. So, we do have an option. We've already been adjusting. The in-person workshops are a two-and-a-half-hour workshop. There's a workshop November 7th.

Yvonne Ivey

So yes, to answer your question... we recognize that we don't have to reinvent the wheel. You've already named two organizations that *literally* have had done this before. And we found that there are over 100 organizations that have done this and that if our goal is to teach an entry level open science to novice and advanced practitioners... we don't have to create new content. We can leverage content that has already been developed. We can teach principles; we can teach practice. We can have conversations to learn where people are... and so the meeting that Chelle was referencing... we were invited to talk about open science for two hours at a science team meeting. And we thought... why not just create some slides and have some conversations and see how this goes?

Let's invite experts and talk to these students... about this... about what we want to do. We realized that... to kick this off, we're probably going to keep stumbling... but instead of being afraid of that, why not lean in? But I think your point is... we have folks who are willing to help.

Chelle Gentemann

So, we have the timelines, we have the workshops, we have the AGU workshops in December. There's four workshops... there's Saturday, Sunday and then Wednesday workshops at AGU. I think that we have a plan to have people who are good facilitators, who are familiar with the material teach those. We have a rough outline in our head of how that will go.

Monica??

That loosely draws from the core material...

Chelle Gentemann

That draws from the community developed Ethos. And right now, I think... again that the in-person workshop is going to be different than the written text that has been developed for the online course and that actually makes it a little easier to get the workshop materials because you're creating slides and these will evolve... So, this is... we don't have really hard and fast deadlines, but we need some initial content for the AGU Fall meeting. We need some initial content for April 1st. We would like to... I totally agree with... let's pause and talk about governance. Let's talk about roles and responsibilities, attribution and... find a path forward. My concern is that based on a lot of the comments ... again, we have these two separate products and as panelists... do you think that that for TOPS... is a strategy that will result in the best content or should we be trying to work on a different strategy?

Isabella Martinez

Jim, you're on the speaker list.

[1:43:16]

Brooks Hanson???

Certainly, I'm not completely sure where to start. So... we've been proceeding on the forked model... based on directions we've been given... and have invested a lot of effort into that, including getting it ready for learning, which we haven't... which needs a lot of feedback. Absolutely. We're comfortable, quite comfortable... with making sure the foundational material was put out there open and continued to develop and provide richness for... and we had discussed with the SMEs ability to support that and NASA's ability to support that going forward.

So... quite comfortable and have invested quite a bit of our effort, community effort, our team's effort and have planned for this schedule going forward. We obviously want very high-quality content, but we're trying to meet those requirements for the MVP... like I said, most of which came after... projects... So that was where the forked model evolved... was to meet those MVPs while still trying to respect the foundational material ... more than we have now. So that's... I think we have a good start on that. But **obviously it needs to be high quality and resonate with the researchers and help develop both in the science and the community.**

So, certainly can go slower, get more feedback on that, improve it... better. And make it better than it is.

Jim

So, I want to speak in the role that Kevin described us in... I'm imagining now that I'm a board member advising the CEO of this operation.

Chelle

There's no Advisory Council... we're getting advice.

Jim

I mean, you know, okay, maybe I'm exaggerating the role, but opinionated.

Chelle

Opinionated, yes.

Jim Colliander??

I view my role as trying to contribute ideas as best as I can to ensure the success of TOPS. And the outcomes of TOPS are... a transformation in the way that we do science with a five-year time horizon. We have a strategy that we're trying to implement, which involves teaching the scientific community at large what open science is and a process was launched with... maybe too little forethought in which a publisher, AGU... a society, AGU was animated.

The process involved hiring some, mostly mid-career to junior career scholars who are subject matter experts to create content. And then this content was going to be filtered in with guidance from NASA and AGU **to create a product that is really a NASA product. It's the NASA TOPS curriculum.** It isn't Malvika's... document. It's a NASA document. But the process of the relationship between the SMEs, who were paid a little bit... of money but mostly honor, and AGU in managing all of that, it seems to have been maybe not a nightmare, but it's a problem, right.

But I want TOPS curriculum launched as soon as possible so that we can get underway on the TOPS mission. So, you have to smooth out these problems between the creators of content and the publisher that manage the SMEs. And so forth, we've got to get past that. So, **I strongly suggest that that gets handled again in a forum maybe with a facilitator**... how far apart are these forks?

If Malavika taught her fork and someone else came in and taught your fork, then who's going to... the students are going to benefit at the end. And so, **I just want to re refocus our attention on we have to take care of these mid-career folks that feel like they're not getting treated right. We've got to fix that.**

And that's really on NASA I think because the system was set up in such a way that AGU was beholden to NASA and therefore is following the fork that NASA appears to be endorsing. I want to assert, as Kevin said and Chelle said, this is NASA's program and NASA might step on some toes because things didn't go right on the launch.

But this is the kind of organization that puts people on the moon. And we get past it because we collectively celebrate rather than individually get attributed. So, I want to endorse your authority

to make these decisions, and I want to recognize you as the world class leader, which is why you're in the seat and smoothing these things out.

So, I'm trying to empower you to fix it so that these mid-career people are protected. And let me get back on task of figuring out what this curriculum is so that we can move forward on open science. I hope that didn't bother the mid-career folks that I'm trying to protect, but we got to get past it. We got to find a way to find the solution and get back on delivery in this context.

So, I don't want to delay. I want to fix it and move fast.

SherAaron

Alright. Couple of things. So curious... where is the content now for us as the panel to review? I don't know if I missed that or not... but is it somewhere so that we can review it?

Brooks Hanson

So, the foundational content... I believe the SMEs are in the process of... posting that.

Yvonne

Yo just said she can do it by the end of lunch.

SherAaron

Thank you.

Brooks

So, the other content we're happy to share at any stage... with NASA's permission.

Chelle Gentemann

We want everything in the open. I'll say it again. I'll say it again. Everything in the open. CC-0 CC-BY. That's all we have. Yeah. Credit to those who contributed. Right. Like specific credit to those who contributed.

SherAaron

Okay. And again... this is clearly for my sake, but so... I'm hearing there's two different forks and I understand the process of how it's been going. But I guess my question is the content that *is* developed, **how do we feel about that content that's developed now?** Is that where we we're back at the drawing board or is it right now we're just not pleased with the process?

Are we not pleased with the process *and* pleased with the work that's being developed?

Chelle Gentemann

I think NASA is pleased with both versions. I think we've had the most time to review the community's developed version and we're really happy with all of that. Every time I read it, I feel like I learn something new because it brings this global perspective and deepens my experience about open science. I think it is absolutely wonderful. I also think there's certainly some things... I would have comments on... just like anything that I read... none of that... what

AGU has done also has value. And there again, I have they've already gotten some of my comments because they asked for them and there was a place to provide them.

Brooks

So... we're going to make that open, Chelle.

Chelle Gentemann

So, both of them are valuable. And the part that I struggle with is the authorship for the AGU content. Honestly, I struggle with understanding the authorship there. The authorship for the community developed content is really crystal clear to me. It is the people who contributed to that and I want to see their ORCID's get credit for that.

So, when we're developing... we try to develop some slides from Ethos that... just I'm sharing with you, but it was really easy and straightforward. I don't know... I was upset about something, right? So, I rage-edit slides.

It's healthy and I'm not allowed near the GitHub anymore in the... so, yeah... so we have good content... we're not in a position where I don't think there's any fear that on April 1st, we're not going to have one if not two courses to select from.

SherAaron

Going back to what Penn said about the in-person teaching, that was something that was a concern of mine I meant to bring up... **where is the preparation for the instructors or the trainers to get trained... that's not listed on this platform?** So, I definitely want to hear what *that's* about. Carpentries specialize in pedagogy of teaching.

Chelle Gentemann

So, I think we're going to revisit that. Because we... I don't think we thought this through completely. And I see Brooks nodding along... we have struggled... clearly, we have struggled to create safe, inclusive environments.... *Unintentionally*... unintentionally. Everybody has the best of intentions, but we have struggled like other people before us. So, I think that that is something that we want to focus on... in the train the trainer is... and I think clearly Carpentries excels at that.

Just so lucky you're here... and then with the content... AGU... I think has committed to... doing a virtual training...

Brooks

A virtual...yes... early familiarization...

SherAaron

And that's the learning, the content? And then my last thing, which I think might have been covered...

Chelle

But I guess one thing to clarify is that NASA will be determining what that content is.

SherAaron

Last question... are there *metrics* or a rubric or something that was developed to say, hey, this is what we want the content to... that way we can put it against each other.

Brooks Hanson

So um, that is being... so we are ready to put in draft and that sort of, like I said... the model we're working from. And then I want to say one thing in response to Jim too... its own response onto... The model where we have a first draft of the assessment... some of this was in a foundation, the SMEs provided some assessment aspects and more on what went into what a beginning researcher should expect to know and learn following each course.

Absolutely, we need improvement and review of whatever input feedback... are these the right assessments... and feedback again from researchers as they take the course and... is it too hard, is it too easy? You all have taught... it's media you all have type you know and you know does this work for the students? This is not work for the students. Do they get it?

Do they not get it? But on a on a set of we expect a beginning researcher, opinion, oftentimes researcher to know this coming out, of course, and to take this forward and send another part of that was developing a using the course materials to... and other resources references and things like that... to develop an open science action plan work and slash their team.

The one thing I just want to... and I didn't say this at the beginning... [because] I wanted to dive in and do things like that... when I talk... when I usually present that first line there is *such* an opportunity on open... we are at a point where... globally... institutions UNESCO, us, we are committed to open science. This is such an opportunity. I really don't want to lose this opportunity. I really want to fix this and develop this going forward... and obviously make TOPS succeed and make all the other cultural changes that we see... that it is such an opportunity and it is *so* important for society, not just science...it is so important. So, thanks, everybody, for the SMEs in particular for your patience and help... and really valuable input into this. And if *we* can do something to help make this work out and fix... because the bigger challenges await us.

Isabella

Thank you. I think Malvika, we'll let you go and then I think we'll take our break after Malvika has finished her comment/question.

[1:56:59]

Malvika

I want to go back to the question that Chelle, you asked... there is this community and process aspect emerging and there's this content aspect emerging... how do we actually address that? Do we address that together? Do we address that separately? And I thought it would be useful for me to... share about how we did that in the Turing Way... you can take that forward or not.

So of course, you want to... a friend and colleague of the Turing way. She calls a *lightly opinionated guide*. So that gives people some sort of authority to be opinionated forward like each... but be very specific when things come to citation... it's a lot about citation because

you're trying to develop something... in the Turing Way was very much like you know such a small Wikipedia of data science... so we're not writing exhaustive thing... we're giving lots of citation and lots of links for people to go out and explore... adventure... whatever that looks like for them.

I clearly remember 2019 September; we sat down with a group of people who we really trusted around making decisions. How do we actually proceed with expansion of the book? Because we started as a book on reproducibility and then we immediately realized it's not just about... tools of reproducibility... but it's really about how we engage... how we're designing the project, how we're collaborating with people, what is ethical responsibility we have?

And in that, we also said... let's do whatever we are doing, whatever we're writing... we need to replicate that doing the Turing Way as a research project. So, it's not just a thing that we are putting out there. There's a process involved in there and taking inspiration from The Carpentries... we created a community handbook... so it wasn't about that committee handbook had the process all figured out. It's something that we are still currently developing. The processes are being written as we learn... the new event gets created, we go back and write, how did we create that event? What was the process? Where are the templates that people want to reproduce that event? Code of conduct... have a very, very clear code of conduct. Of course, you have NASA code of conduct, NASA policy that likes them, but then give an opportunity for external people to get involved, have that bifurcation, if you can... This is what happens if you're not a NASA employee, this is what happens. But the baseline as far as we want you to be respectful and of all the people that you actually already have... contribution guideline write like and we are going to super basic here so I think get you to a repository put it read me for what we are doing.

Contribution guidelines... how are people contributing? What our different ways to contribute... having us and... we don't need to even start [from] scratch. There are so many brilliant contribution guidelines out there for content development and acknowledgment process, right? Again, like in the Carpentries... we see that a lot in terms of people getting roles and certification and getting the space to talk... in the Turing Way, we have very transient role because people are author one day and their reviewer one day and their speaker one day. So, we can't really give that... specific role. But our acknowledgment process, Kristina??? and I sat down and wrote like multiple documents about what it looks like if you fix bugs... what it looks like if you created a placeholder story... what it looks like if you go out and talk about the Turing Way.

So, having that process as like if I was contributing to some other community and I was doing this... what it would look like... and eventually it was all about what do they find meaningful? It's not about what *I* think is incentive for them, but asking them... what kind of incentives we all for what is most meaningful for you if you're here for today, take whatever you need and go. But we recognize it. But if you're here for a longer term, we'll give you another way to be elevated in the community. So have that again... I'm really proud of the work we've done in the Turing Way and the processes that we've written. And it's all 50 by 4.2???. Thank you, Monica. So please do take them, you know, thank them, start them.

I'm not saying that it's perfect for you, but it's always better to start from some draft so you can ... completely re-imagine what that looks like for you. Going back again to... reimagining openness in different projects, right? So, we're not teaching people that this is what NASA thinks is open science. NASA is introducing you to a framework of openness.

So, in the Turing Way we phrase it as... that we want to build a resource where... group leaders or legal researcher as funders, policymaker, whatever. They'll come and understand what is their responsibility of reproducibility. And we want to actually... what we want to do in TOPS is that we want people to understand what is *your* responsibility of openness, how much can you impact?

It's not your sole responsibility. You need to share it. So it's possible that we come up with much longer content and not *all* the content will be delivered to the same person. It's like a LEGO, you can pull and choose and do whatever you want. And a final one is the train the trainer pedagogy ... that doesn't depend on content you're dealing with. Pedagogy is super transferable. You don't need to wait for the content to be developed in order to conduct that kind of training. That's already... bringing people into... they're buying into the system and they say, Oh yeah, we're prepared to teach whatever you have and will have a say in what is happening. Because I think one of my biggest concerns is... that all these external people are telling us what to do. And they're like the presence of NASA researchers would be like... what do they know about NASA? But they would completely reject that material. Say, we don't really know what you're doing, but **there is like this early buy-in is important from people who are into the system, want to teach it, bring them into the review or comment process, run some focus groups as well.**

So, it's not just about what SMEs are saying or what module leads are saying or what AGU is saying or what people sitting in the room are saying. Go to different rooms, run focus group on on understanding. And of course, you don't need to take all those comments. It will make you see that two-and-a-half hours are not enough to teach anything, people need to just get that taste operate. And what I learned from the Carpentries... is that we start our training, carpentry, straining... saying that we're not here to teach you everything. We're going to get through whatever we can. **But my aim here as a teacher is to give you enough confidence that enough understanding that when you leave this room, you would understand better.** You would... the learning mindset.

So how do you become from novice to expert is your own journey. So here we're just... I think there's a lot of like we've already discussed this. This room has so much shared understanding. I promise you... you wouldn't start from scratch. We're very, very honored and very happy to share all of this with you.

Yvonne Ivey

Thank you, both. Folks, let's take a five minute break.

Participants return from the break.

Thanks, everyone, we're coming back from break. And it looks like Monika in the room has a question. Comment?

Monica

Yeah, a comment. I can just with the intention of trying to help you focus as much as possible and the recognition that you folks are *very good* at asking for help, and that's really, I think, a sign and symbol of a good team. And so, try to condense what I've been hearing... it sounds like your timelines won't be jeopardized because you have an abundance of material that you can draw from to create the things that you need to for these for these deadlines...right... what your biggest obstacle is... trying to figure out, like you said, what to do with these forks and also make sure that the community that created them is respected both on the side of AGU and of course, also from the SMEs.

And so... I wonder if, you know, your next step... I think needs to be to schedule that meeting is the facilitator and **Daniela and my colleague at pre-review** the name that... she was excellent. So then try to figure out... whether you keep those two separates and let's let those two stakeholders make that decision. And I wonder if one of the things that you can consider in that discussion process, because ultimately that should be between those parties that make that decision... is whether you do keep two separate things. One, that is... long and full of information that you pull from to create your deliverables, to meet your timelines. And the other that is sort of led by... but that has sort of more of the AGU hand... you figure out what is the best use of... that... condensed material, for lack of a better word.

What if you looked at 'what are the deliverables you need to meet in the future' and could you iterate on that to meet one of your deliverables? And then what you do is you keep the community built or the longer the larger content to pull from for your... the other deliverables that you have for the Year of Open Science... now just so it's a suggestion... so rather than the sort of we'll call it the AGU version being the where you pull from information or that sort of being the version of record... that... becomes a specific if use for one of your deliverables and for everything else that you need, you just pull from that larger foundational material that was built from the community. Now, it's only for your consideration, and I think it's up to those two parties... at this facilitator led discussion, to make that decision... but it sounds like your timelines won't be jeopardized and I think that's that sounds that sounds good.

Logan???

You know, this is not a fully formed thought. So I'm interested in pushback, if folks don't think that is... that if it doesn't resonate or sound like a good idea, but I just wanted to toss out the idea that that just **the usage of the facilitator may sort of mask some of the underlying problem**, which is that **there's this lack of governance** and the reality is... working in the open source space.

It would be great if you could just... you're having a conversation or pull request or something and people aren't aligning on their vision... you just bring in a facilitator. But I don't think that the reality is... that's [not] feasible from a long-term standpoint and maybe it only needs to happen this one time... but I would be concerned that... that would again mask the reality that **there isn't this well-documented process** with all the information accessible to everybody, which is what it sounds like caused the misalignment of what's happened.

Chelle Gentemann

I think that this goes back a little bit to what Monica said. If there's two products, then I think they each need to work on developing their own governance, rules, definitions... clearly. If they come together, then they need to come together and agree exactly what that governance structure looks like. But I do agree that's kind of... I'm sorry, I don't know who's first...

SherAron

I guess my question is... if there were these two distinct things, again, me not having seen them, not knowing what they are about... but... is there a way to say, hey, we use this one in this case and we use *this* one in this case type thing, or just throwing it out there.

Fernando Perez

This is Fernando from Berkeley. As I listen to Monica, it kind of occurred to me that... I just went through an experience similar to this one. And I wanted to share briefly. It may not overgeneralize, but at least to the extent that it helps. I just realized that a few weeks ago we had a similar version of something like this, but on a smaller scale and it worked well.

So, I wanted to try to share *why* it worked well so last year. So, Chelle will know what this is about... I moderated a panel at CCI with an Argentinian and a Colombian researcher about open source in Latin America, and our notes were longer than what we can do it verbally during the meeting. So, we prepared it as a blog post and we asked CCI whether they would be willing to share it. And so, the example here is that... we were kind of that little group of three SMEs, the people from Latin America, CCI would give us the implementor of this very respected organization that could publicize it. And they said, Oh yes, for sure. The Argentinian researcher who's a fundamental change is kind of a sister organization or philosophically aligned with the Carpentries in Argentina. Her team translated our content to Spanish and Portuguese because we wanted really to engage with the Latin American community. It would be kind of ironic to do it in English.

The CCI editorial team wanted... ours was a little longer and whatnot... they said, for our audience and for the organization, we want a more tightly edited version. So, the English version on the CCI side was much shorter in the end. They did a *phenomenal* job. They brought a professional science comm (communication) person who edited really tightly, our content. But in the end, we didn't feel disrespected, we didn't feel not listened to... **there was a partnership in the process** of how... what their intent... was to have something that for us was beneficial and that we would get. And I'm imagining for many SMEs, having the voice of NASA/AGU to you can be professional beneficial for us that was the case. But in return, they explained that they had editorial constraints they needed to meet and we saw their editing process, right? And they shared that. And so, it was an example... a baby version and obviously much easier... I'm trying to offer this as a constructive example of how that dialogue was established productively and both... I think **in the end, all parties benefited. The final product was fully cross-linked.** So, the CCI blog post has links to the ???... the long, the English, Spanish and Portuguese versions, and vice versa and ours... and we cross publicized. And in the end, I think it was a kind of a healthy outcome, both for the community version and for the more official, more tightly edited version published by CCI. So perhaps that can be... an illustration of how to succeed in merging those competing needs.

[2:11:31]

Monica

It just made me think that it may be worthwhile to think about... **what do you want to have before you go into this meeting with the facilitator and for both parties**... maybe you already have a proposed governance to come forward... so that it's an even more productive meeting. Have an idea of... what is going to be that editorial process. This is a proposed process so that you have something to discuss and either converge together or again separately. But, I'm very well prepared, I think, to that... to that meeting with some deliverables.

Chelle Gentemann

I like that suggestion... it resonates with me... that NASA can... say this is what we're looking for and then have the facilitator work with both groups to find out... what we can... where we can meet.

Speaker???

I just want to highlight that there's a lot of other content in Brooks's slides, and so people may want to look through those slides because I think there's other learning there. And then I just want to point out that we're into Chelle's wrap up, I think.

Chelle Gentemann

We have 12 minutes left. I think... let's give the next 7 minutes to Brooks, because there's a lot... I think that... there's been *a lot* going on today. And maybe Brooks wants to show some of the other content. Maybe he wants to have some closing comments.

But let's... if you're willing, Brooks... then I'd like to give you some time and then I'll do the wrap up in like 5 minutes.

Brooks Hanson

So, as I started... there's a...so thanks to everyone here and online for the conversation. As I said in response to Jim, I do think this is a really special time and I hope that we find the right way so we can take advantage of it... we can change the culture. It's important. Really important. So, thank you everybody for working through the difficulties and keeping the eyes on the prize.

There's a lot of other exciting things going on... that if we get this right, it will eat into... and then I think also I'll echo what Kevin has said... I don't know if Kevin is still here... we're learning as we go and we're really trying to improve as we go and... not just on this content, but a lot of the other things that we and other societies and members of a whole bunch of communities are doing.

[There are] really some great opportunities to work together on some of this. Some of this was in the other slide. I will say... we are planning an Open Science plenary at our Fall meeting. So hopefully many of you can get there... it'll be two hours on Friday. We're hoping that again, the NASA chief scientist or other appropriate person will moderate that. Monica is participating in one of the panels. We have a keynote... and it will be our theme for next year and something that we're broadly committed to going forward. Culture change is really hard. **We're looking**

forward to helping reach a lot more than 20,000 signups. Just for example, there is another slide... we have 900 editors, so that's 5% already of who we'd like to engage in this. We actually have about 60,000 members... 140,000 co-authors on abstracts of ... over three or four years... Unique coauthors participating with you regularly. So we're in touch with... I mentioned 300 repositories in this space. All those users that really could benefit from open science awareness. And that's just in the Earth and Space science has many other partnerships working with NIH, NSF and so forth.

So, I really think this is an opportunity... and then a variety of collaborations with EGU/EU and others. There's some strong resistance to... other of their conversations... Chris and others, we've just been in conversations with two major modeling centers in the EU. Absolutely won't release their code. What they said to us is: 'we're going to publish in journals that we don't have to release our code from.' So, there's some strong institutional resistance and that's in the EU where getting like, oh, there a little more ahead and things like that. Maybe in five years we'll have a process or governance process to release our code and thanks. So I think that that's model and centers are a great example and but climate modeling and NOAA modeling or we've had more productive conversations... but that was two weeks ago and that's a direct quote "we're going to publish somewhere else"... so we don't have to release our code.

So, there is going to be some institutional resistance that we have to get around. And there are some societies, that are you know, Monica... we're dealing with one right now that... our journal won't accept a CC license on a preprint limited do something... so there there's some culture change that are institutional, not just at the personal level that we're going to have to address in our community and other communities and look forward to all of your help doing this.

But there's so much online right now from carrots and sticks and peers and examples of how valuable this is and so forth. And I'm really optimistic with the right pushes and training and awareness and... we're seeing a lot of non-awareness of... oh it's a little more hassle to do the right thing, oh.... I get these tremendous benefits... and can we help share that.

So, I'm very optimistic about where we can be by the end of five years and even accelerated from that, really happy to be part of this. I'm really happy to have met a lot of... new communities and new colleagues as part of this, and I hope we can find a good path forward that can strengthen these relationships for what we all want.

Thank you, Brooks.

And I'll just stop there. But if I think... the slides you shared, we are happy to respond or add depth. I've been told for me... never put notes on PowerPoint. So, I don't put notes on my PowerPoint because they totally distract me from what I'm trying to say. So, I realize there's just a lot of bullets there without sometimes context or things like that.

So, if any of you have questions... I think my email is on the first slide. If it's not it's... And I do have to catch a plane tonight because we're running a workshop to try to get... I wanted to mention this convert it... to try to get community science funded, 30 or \$40 million in NSF. So that's tomorrow. Laura's helping on that. And that to me is also a key part of open science... is

getting that community engagement and the broader impacts of grants engaged in community science and open science is really important for that. So that's tomorrow. So, I have to fly back to help run that... Laura's staying here and helping run that tomorrow.

So, but Laura and Kristina are here this afternoon. So if you have other questions, feel free to ask them if they can answer it. So refer back to us. So, I am going to apologize. I'm going to leave right after lunch because I have to get to the airport.

Kevin Murphy

Yeah. Hey, everybody. I'm actually *just* about to be on the plane, so I'll make my comment short. I have been listening all morning. I think the discussion that we've had is invaluable. I really do appreciate... the advisory group or... the review panel's comments and... the comments from the SMEs and AGU... relative to how do we move this forward. There are a lot of options. We're learning this. And I think how we move it... this is a good opportunity for us to continue to... begin building that trust necessary to really make a good set of things to change the community perspective. So just thank you very much for participating. Keep the honest feedback coming and really hope to see you again in person soon.

Chelle

Thank you. Have a good flight, Kevin.

Kevin

Thank you.

Chelle Gentemann

Thanks for coming out... so we're going to wrap up on time and we're getting kicked out. Otherwise, we'll miss the tour.

I want to really recognize how hard this morning was... and I really want to thank everyone for, like Kevin said... helping us improve, helping us get better, giving us honest feedback... how we are acting as a funding agency and impacting this community... in ways that we've certainly never intended... how we were working with other groups and navigating all of that.

What I really heard is... we're going to start down this path of creating the outline, working with facilitators, slowing down, pausing... and being much more intentional about our actions. Thank you. Thank you for that feedback and that guidance... and the conversation about governance and I hope that we will... I'm certain we *will* have a path forward and I'm hoping that we can find a place that everyone... maybe isn't perfectly happy, but is happy *enough* that we are going forward.

Because, like Brooks said... this is so much bigger than just us, and just this one thing. There is this giant prize that awaits us... which is improving science and making science more equitable, more just and creating room so that more people have a seat at the table. And I know that I speak for probably every single person in the room... that we are all incredibly passionate about what changing... in what not just what science looks like, but the ecosystem that science exists and how it's working today versus how we want it to work tomorrow.

And thank you *so* much for being part of this process. The next steps are... that we will create a transcript. So, this will be similar to the spring panel. We'll create a transcript of both days and we will post that on a Google Docs... just like Spring... we're going to be completely open, transparent. We'll have a writer go in and start organizing and editing... and everyone's welcome to pitch in and do that too... and then... bring it to you and it'll all be open the whole time that we get this more organized content. So, for you to then start drawing recommendations from... and a report that will come back to us in 30 days that we'll then use to move forward into the next period.

And part of that will be that we're going to meet more often and we'll be in discussion with you about that. So, thanks so much.

END OF TRANSCRIPT